

Wind Energy as A Source of Sustainable Energy in India: A Statistical Overview

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Abstract Wind is a discontinuous and site-specific resource of RE and India currently has the fourth highest wind install capacity in the world. India is blessed with a coastline of about 7600 km surrounded by water on three sides and has good prospects of harnessing offshore wind energy. India has set a goal of harnessing 140 GW (out of which 30 GW is offshore wind) installed wind energy capacity by 2030[1]. This paper provides an overview on India's wind energy current scenario and future forecast (by 2030). The least square method is used to calculate year wise trend and the model considered in the paper is tested using Chi-square test and from results of the test it is observed that the linear trend line is of best fit and there is no significant difference between observed and expected generation of wind power over the time.

Keywords Renewable Energy, Trend, Chi-square test.

Introduction India is the 7th country by area, the 2nd populous country in the world [2]and its demand of energy is increasing rapidly and limited conventional resources and climate-changing problems associated with them underline the need for new and sustainable energy supply options that use different sources of RE. For now, green and clean energy is considered to be an important criterion for sustainable development of any country.

Objective of study To confirm India's ambition of installed wind energy capacity by 2030.

Review of Literature **Sims** [11] compares the costs of renewable energy systems with fossil fuel-derived energy services and considers how placing a value on carbon emissions will help provide convergence. **Jorge** [12] reviews the prospects for RE as a source of electricity in Mexico. In this study, it is concluded that Mexico is at crossroads with respect to renewable energy. **Frede** [13] analyze two RE governance systems in relation to a set of main characteristics of RE systems, which should be taken into consideration when establishing a RE institutional framework. In the description above he also emphasized an institutional context which will be able to "catch" some useable analytical results within these RE characteristics. **Kumar** et al. [10] examines some aspects of Renewable energy for sustainable development in India as current status, future prospects, challenges, employment, and investment opportunities. **Paliwal** et al. [9] reviews the availability and current status of RE in Rajasthan and also an attempt is made to summarize the availability and utilization of RE sources in Rajasthan using various charts (pie, bar, histogram etc.) for representation and comparison of districts of Rajasthan. **Bhukya** [8] has done a study on the potential and opportunities of electric power generation through renewable energy in the state of Rajasthan. **Swarnkar** et al. [7] investigated the Indian renewable energy Scenario based on survey data and also find the energy potential of India in terms of sources, per-capita energy consumption. In this paper two statistical analysis are proposed. One is the statistical analysis of installed capacity, generation and consumption of fossil fuels and renewable energy in India and other one is the statistical analysis of two solar power plants located at different geographical locations in India.

Main Text

Potential of Wind Energy in India:

The Ministry, through National Institute of Wind Energy (NIWE), has installed 967 wind-monitoring stations all over the country and issued wind potential maps at 50 m, 80 m, 100 m and 120 m above ground level.

The latest assessment indicates gross wind power

potential of 302.25 GW and 695.50 GW in the country at 100-meter and 120 meters respectively, above ground level. Most of this potential exists in seven windy states in table 1 and fig.1[5].

Installed capacity of Wind Power in the country:

The installed capacity of grid-interactive wind power in the country as on 31.12.2021 is 40.0827 GW and state-wise installed capacity (in MW) is shown in table 2 and fig.2[1].

Table 1: Potential of Wind Energy in India		
S. No.	State	Wind Power Potential at 120 mtragl (GW)
1	Andhra Pradesh	74.9
2	Gujarat	142.56
3	Karnataka	124.15

4	Madhya Pradesh	15.4
5	Maharashtra	98.21
6	Rajasthan	127.75
7	Tamil Nadu	68.75
8	Other States	43.78
All India Total		695.5
Source: MNRE https://mnre.gov.in		

Table 2: Installed capacity of Wind Power in the country

S. No.	State	Installed Capacity (MW)
1	Andhra Pradesh	4096.65
2	Gujarat	9007.72
3	Karnataka	5077.2
4	Madhya Pradesh	2519.89
5	Maharashtra	5012.83
6	Rajasthan	4326.82
7	Tamil Nadu	9846.69
8	Telangana	128.10
9	Kerala	62.5
10	Others	4.30
Total		40082.7
Source: MNRE https://mnre.gov.in		

Fig.2: State-wise Wind Power Installed Capacity (in MW)

Share of Wind Energy in total energy:

As on 30-dec-22, share of wind power in total energy is 10.2% including both offshore and onshore wind generation across India which is shown in table 3 and fig.3.

Category	Installed Generation Capacity (MW)	% of Share in Total
Fossil Fuel		
Coal	2,03,985	49.90%
Lignite	6,620	1.60%
Gas	24,824	6.10%
Diesel	589	0.10%
Total Fossil Fuel	2,36,019	57.90%
Non-Fossil Fuel		
RES (Incl. Hydro)	1,66,362	40.70%
Hydro	46,850	11.50%
Wind, Solar & Other RE	1,19,512	29.20%
Wind	41,895	10.20%
Solar	61,966	15.10%
BM Power/Cogen	10,206	2.50%
Waste to Energy	520	0.10%
Small Hydro Power	4,925	1.20%
Nuclear	6,780	1.70%
Total Non-Fossil Fuel	1,73,142	42.30%
Total Installed Capacity (Fossil Fuel & Non-Fossil Fuel)	4,09,161	100%

Source: <https://powermin.gov.in>

Methodology and Statistical tools:

Data collection: Secondary data is taken from MNRE generation report.

Scatter plot: On the basis of scatter plot (between Year's on x-axis and Electricity Generation in GW on y-axis) it is observed that a straight line is best suited to forecast the wind power generation.

Fig.4: Scatter plot

Least square method: From above plot consider a straight-line equation as

$$\hat{y} = a + bX$$

Where variable \hat{y} represents Generation (in GW), variable X represents Time (in Years) and a and b are constants to be obtained using the method of least squares.

To calculate these constants (a and b) for 'n' observations (x_i, y_i and $i=1,2,3,\dots,n$) the normal equations are:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n y_i = n \times a + b \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i = a \sum_{i=1}^n x_i + b \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

Goodness of fit test (chi-square test):

To test the line obtained from the method of least squares the chi-square(χ^2) test is performed and test statistic is given by:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Where O_i are the observed values and E_i are the expected values (obtained from the trend line fitted from method of least squares) of the wind energy generation in GW.

Null hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant difference between Observed (O_i) and expected (E_i) generation of wind energy over the time.

Alternative hypothesis (H_1): There is significant difference between observed (O_i) and expected (E_i) generation of wind energy over the time.

Decision criteria:

If $\chi^2_{cal} \leq \chi^2_{tab}$, at (n-1) d.f. with level of significance (α), Accept H_0 i.e. There is no significant difference between Observed (O_i) and expected (E_i) generation of wind energy over the time.

And if $\chi^2_{cal} \geq \chi^2_{tab}$ at (n-1) d.f. with level of significance (α), Reject H_0 i.e. There is significant difference between observed (O_i) and expected (E_i) generation of wind energy over the time.

Graphical representation:

Bar plot: It is plotted between Year's (on x-axis) and Electricity Generation in GW (on y-axis). From the plot, we can conclude that there exists an increasing trend in the wind power generation (in GW) as time (year's) increases.

Fig.5: Bar plot of Wind energy generation year-wise

Statistical analysis:

regression line using least square method:

S. No.	X	Y	$X - M_x$	$Y - M_y$	$(X - M_x)^2$	$(X - M_x)(Y - M_y)$
1	2015	32.74	-3	-21.68	9	65039.598
2	2016	43.46	-2	-10.96	4	21922.11
3	2017	52.62	-1	-1.79	1	1796.29
4	2018	60.31	0	5.89	0	0
5	2019	63.31	1	8.89	1	8892.96
6	2020	60.40	2	5.98	4	11962.47
7	2021	68.09	3	13.67	9	41018.99
Total					$SS_x: 28$	$SP_{xy}: 150.62$

Where Year =X, Generation In GW =Y

Calculation Summary:

Sum of X = 14126

Sum of Y = 380.93

Mean X (M_x)= 2018

Mean Y(M_y)= 54.4186

Sum of squares (SS_x) = 28

Sum of products (SP_{xy}) = 150.62

Regression Equation = $\hat{y} = bX + a$

$b = SP_{xy}/SS_x = (150.62/28) = 5.37929$

$a = M_y - bM_x = 54.42 - (5.38*2018) = -10800.98$

$\hat{y} = 5.37929X - 10800.98$... (3)

$$R^2 = \frac{SS_{\text{Regression}}}{SS_{\text{total}}} = \frac{\sum(\hat{y}_i - M_y)^2}{\sum(y_i - M_y)^2} = \frac{810.3617}{929.891} = 0.8715$$

Confidence Interval:

The confidence interval is the prediction interval for the mean value of the dependent variable.

Calculating the standard error:

$$S.E.^2_{ci} = S^2_{\text{residual}} \left(\frac{1}{n} + \frac{(X_0 - \bar{X})^2}{SS_x} \right)$$

$$S.E.^2_{ci} = (4.8894)^2 \left(\frac{1}{7} + \frac{(2030 - 2018)^2}{28} \right) = (11.241)^2$$

S.E.ci = 11.241

Calculating the confidence interval:

$$\hat{Y} \pm T_{1-\alpha/2}(n-2) * S.E_{ci}$$

$$118.978 \pm T_{1-0.05/2}(7-2) * S.E_{ci}$$

$$118.978 \pm 2.5706 * 11.241 \Sigma$$

C.I.=[90.0822, 147.8738]

Chi-square test (Goodness of fit test)

4.4 Chi-square test:

Table 05: Calculation for Chi-square test				
S. No.	Year (X)	O_i	E_i	$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$
1	2015	32.74	38.2894	0.8039
2	2016	43.46	43.6686	0.0010
3	2017	52.62	49.0479	0.2609
4	2018	60.31	54.4272	0.6361
5	2019	63.31	59.8065	0.2057
6	2020	60.40	65.1858	0.3510
7	2021	68.09	70.5651	0.0865
Total		380.95	380.99	2.35

From the table above chi square calculated = 2.35 with 6 degrees of freedom and critical value (or tabulated value) of chi-square = 12.596 at 95% confidence interval with 6 degrees of freedom.

Since, $\chi^2_{cat} < \chi^2_{tab}$ at 6 d.f. and $\alpha=0.05$

Therefore, do not reject H_0 i.e. There is no significant difference between Observed (O_i) and expected (E_i) generation of wind energy over the time.

4.5 Estimated wind power generation for the year 2030:

The linear trendline is

$$\hat{y} = 5.37929X - 10800.98$$

and the Estimated wind power generation for the year 2030 is as:

Fig. 6:Fitted Straight line and predicted value for year 2030

Year(X)	Generation in GW (Y) prediction
2030	118.978

Conclusion The data obtained from year's 2015-2021 a linear trend is obtained using least square method. Using chi-square goodness of fit test, it is observed that the trend line is of best fit and there is no significant difference between observed and expected generation of wind power. This study confirms India's ambition of harnessing 140 GW of installed wind energy capacity by 2030, as the predicted generation for 2030 is 118.978 GW, which is fairly near to the actual figure.

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